

The Influence of Social Media Endorsement on Customer Purchase Decision

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ABSTRACT: Celebrity social media endorsement has become a popular marketing strategy over the last decade. However, it is not always effective in the consumer purchase decision process. Sometimes, it brings adverse effects to the brand and product due to the wrong selection of celebrity figures. and for MSME who have limited capital, it is very important to effectively choose celebrities on social media for endorsement so that marketing strategies carried out result in consumer purchase decisions. Therefore, this research aimed to investigate three variables that related to celebrity social media endorsement but had the most significant influence on purchase decisions. Among others: expertise, trustworthiness, and attractiveness so it can be used by marketers or MSME as an insight. This research used a quantitative method to collect the data; there were 205 respondents as a sample. The data will be analyzed with inner and outer models and calculated with PLS statistics. The findings revealed that all variables, including expertise, trustworthiness, and attractiveness, have a positive influence on purchase decisions. However, it is only trustworthiness and attractiveness that have significant influence, with the p-values of trustworthiness (0.042 0.050) and a coefficient obtained of 0.175, which means they have a positive and significant influence also p-values of attractiveness (0.000 0.050) with a coefficient obtained of 0,647, which means a positive and significant influence and expertise had an insignificant influence on purchase decisions with p-values (0.843 > 0.050) and a coefficient of 0.014, which means it had a positive and insignificant influence on purchase decisions. This research has come to the conclusion that MSME may consider applying celebrity social media endorsements to their campaigns, but they must take into account the variables that have a significant influence on the purchase decision. Particularly attractiveness, which had the most significant influence.

KEYWORDS: Attractiveness, Celebrity endorsement, Expertise, Purchase decision, Trustworthiness.

INTRODUCTION

Social media the most popular digital marketing medium, so the online shop flourishes on this platform. the competitiveness of online shops has increased significantly. So the online store started thinking about using marketing strategies. One of the next strategies is celebrity endorsement, which has been widely used over the past decade, whether in print or broadcast advertising. marketing trend #1 in 2023 is small businesses cozying up to creators because, For small businesses, 2023 promises to be a resource-draining year, downsizing and shrinking budgets that will make their toughest marketing challenges even tougher. To ease the pressure, small business owners will start to rely on the very creators abandoned by big business. In general, the price of endorsements has been determined by the creators at the outset before entering into a collaboration; however, the business owner has to pay without knowing the feedback they will get. It is difficult for MSMEs because they need to manage cash flow to run their businesses. Creators cannot be sure how many products will be sold; they only provide a range of engagement and insight information on their social media accounts, so endorsements have not been proven to increase customer purchase decisions. Creators only ensure brand awareness through the viewers and content collaboration they create, which are taken into consideration by various alternatives in customer decision-making. A purchase decision comes from a learning process and a thinking process that shapes perception. This purchase decision creates a driving force that continues to be recorded in the mind and becomes a very strong desire that eventually, when the consumer has to satisfy his need, he will realize those needs. what he has in mind. According to Mowen Stigler in Cobb-Walgren (1995), a brand that is known to the buyer generates interest in making a purchase decision.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Kaplan and Haenlein (2010), p. 61, social media is characterized as "a collection of online applications that utilize the principles and technology of Web 2.0 and that enable the formation and sharing of user-created material". According to Kaplan and Haenlein (2010), the characteristics of social media are as follows: Social media relies on users. Social media platforms would be nothing more than forums and applications without users. The network is populated by conversations and content created by users.

Anyone who participates in the discussion determines the content's direction. For Internet users, this is what makes social networks so much more dynamic and exciting. Social media also has the advantage of being much more interactive than conventional media. Community concepts are the foundation of social networks, which thrive on them. The emotional aspect of social networks is another distinctive feature.

Celebrity Endorsement

According to Widodo (2013:2), Celebrity Endorser is defined as a famous TV star, movie actor, and athlete that has the ability to influence consumers' attitudes and behavior towards advertised products.

Purchase Decision

A consumer makes purchases frequently throughout the day. The purchase itself is the only indication of a more complicated process that a customer goes through for each decision they make. However, every purchase decision differs in terms of time and effort required.

Trustworthiness

Erdogan et al. Trustworthiness can be described as the authenticity, uprightness, and credibility of a person who endorses something (2001). Companies look for endorsers who are regarded as honest, believable, and dependable by a large number of people. Effective endorsers place a significant emphasis on trustworthiness. The believability of the advertisement will rise and consumers' attitudes will improve if they trust the endorser and believe what they hear (Erdogan et al., 2001).

Attractiveness

The idea of attractiveness encompasses more than just physical attractiveness. Concepts like intellectual abilities, personality traits, way of life, athletic performances, and endorser skills are also part of attractiveness (Chaniotakis et al., 2010). Celebrities' physical attractiveness was a significant indicator of how well their advertisements performed. Beautifulness, good looks, and classy elegance were used to measure attractiveness (Chaniotakis et al., 2010). states that consumers are more likely to make a purchase if celebrity endorsers are attractive.

Expertise

According to Erdogan et al., "the extent to which an endorser is perceived to be a source of valid assertions" is the definition of the celebrity endorsement. (2001). Perceptions of the quality of the product are also influenced by expert sources. It has been discovered that the expert source or celebrity is more persuasive and generates more purchase intentions. Its efficiency will be determined by the celebrity's level of expertise (Amos et al., 2008).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Data collection techniques according to Sugiyono (2018) consist of observation, interviews, questionnaires and documentation. In this study, researchers collected data using questionnaire techniques. This research using primary and data source to solve the research problems. Quantitative data is a type of data that can be measured or calculated directly as numbers. The data that author get, will be processed using several tests with PLS Analysis. The test including outer model and inner model. Then the data that has been processed will be analyzed by author to become a business solution. Because this research has a large population and has several criteria, then author decide taking the sample by choose representative sample. The criteria of the sample as follows: Social media user and have made online purchase and Age 20-35 years old. The author using the Table of population or sample determination techniques based on (Dantes, 2012) by categorizing the sample, so the sample in this research is 200 respondents.

Validity Test

The validity test that are conducted for each variable including Expertise (X1) with 6 questions, Trustworthiness (X2) with 7 questions, Attractiveness (X3) with 7 questions and Purchase Decision (Y) with 7 questions. Based on the result, all question items on the Research Instrument have an loading factor > 0.7 . Therefore, it was concluded that all question items on each variable were valid. Which means that If loading factor > 0.7 then the statement is declared valid.

Reliability Test

Reliability testing of the instrument was carried out by testing the scores between items using the Alpha Cronbach technique by comparing the alpha coefficient with 0.700. The set of questions to measure a variable is reliable and successful in measuring the variable we are measuring if the reliability coefficient is greater than or equal to 0.700. Based on the result, it can be seen that the reliability coefficient for all variables is greater than the critical value (0.700), so that all research variables are reliable, thus the instrument can be continued for further analysis.

Coefficient of determination (R²)

The coefficient of determination (R-square) obtained from the first model is the influence of variables X1 (expertise), X2 (Trustworthiness) and X3 (Attractiveness) on Variable Y (Purchase Decision) of 0.597, so that variable Y (Purchase Decision) can be explained by variable X1 (Expertise), X2 (Trustworthiness), and X3 (Attractiveness) of 59.7% and the remaining 40.3% is influenced by other variables outside this study.

Predictive Relevance (Q²)

Based on the results of the Q square calculation indicate that can be explained by the model is 0.365. which means we can concluded that the effects of the three models are included in the strong model category (>0.35).

Effect size (F²)

Based on the results of the Effect size (F²) calculation indicate that the X1 expertise has which means we can concluded that the effects of the three models are included in the strong model category (>0.35).

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Direct Effect of Expertise

The effect of variable X1 (Expertise) on variable Y (Purchase Decision) has a T-statistics value that is smaller than the critical value ($0.198 < 1.960$), and P-values greater than α ($0.843 > 0.05$), therefore, the decision to accept H₀ was obtained with the conclusion that variable X1 (Expertise) had a positive and not significant influence on increasing the variable Y (Purchase Decision).

Direct Effect of Trustworthiness

The effect of variable X2 (Trustworthiness) on variable Y (Purchase Decision) has a T-statistics value greater than the critical value ($2.004 > 1.960$), and p-values smaller than α ($0.042 < 0.05$), therefore a decision is obtained reject H₀ with the conclusion that variable X2 (Trustworthiness) has a positive and significant influence on increasing variable Y (Purchase Decision).

Direct Effect of Attractiveness

The effect of variable X3 (Attractive) on variable Y (Purchase Decision) has a T-statistics value greater than the critical value ($11.408 > 1.960$), and p-values smaller than α ($0.000 < 0.05$), therefore the decision to reject H₀ was obtained with the conclusion that the variable X3 (Attractiveness) had a positive and significant influence on increasing the variable Y (Purchasing Decision).

BUSINESS SOLUTION

From the analysis data that had been conducted, the result for the influence expertise, trustworthiness and attractiveness endorsement of social media celebrity on purchase decision process at MSME is all the variables have a positive effect to independent variable, but only trustworthiness and attractiveness have a significant effect to purchase decision. The solution for MSMEs who wants to use endorsement social media celebrity as marketing based on this research are since there is significant effect of trustworthiness on purchase decision, therefore marketers must find celebrities who have a good and honest image to their followers on social media so that customers can give trust products endorsed by social media celebrities. Honesty is very important to improve their purchase decision and also because attractiveness has a strong significance on purchasing decisions, MSMEs must find USP (Unit Selling Point) and adapt it to the attractiveness of celebrity social media because each celebrity social media has its charms and characteristics, therefore adjust it to the attractiveness of the desired product SMEs show. do this to make the product they advertise look very attractive and fit social media celebrities.

CONCLUSION

There is a positive significant effect of trustworthiness on purchase decision So it means that customer trust in celebrities is very important so that celebrity images are very influential because if celebrity are trusted, then customers can easily made purchase decision. There is a positive significant effect of attractiveness on purchase decision it means attractiveness can stimulates the followers behavior in terms of their popularity and lifestyle so they can attract audience to make purchase decisions. There is a positive insignificant influence of expertise celebrity social media on purchase decision. it means H_3 rejected because participant in this research already have own knowledge about a product and it does not depend on the amount or complete or incomplete information provided by celebrity social media if customer feel attract and trust then it is enough for the customers to make the purchase decision. Therefore, marketers considering celebrity endorsements for their campaigns are advised to consider variables that have a significant impact on their purchasing decisions. In particular, attractiveness had the greatest impact.

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